

Optimize single line to ground fault detection in distribution grid power system using artificial bee colony

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ABSTRACT

The most common power system (PS) distribution network fault, single line-to-ground fault (SLGF), causes residual current (I_{res}) to start an electrical arc and high voltage (HV) three times the rated voltage in other healthy phases. HV from capacitive currents (IC) damages cable insulation and PS appliances. Peterson The neutral point coil (PC) reduces (I_{res}) and extinguishes the electric arc, but the fault current (I_{fault}) remains below the protection devices' threshold. Operations and equipment are riskier. PC adaptive eliminates electrical arcs, making the network safer. This paper detects I faults online using Texas instrument validation in MATLAB and adaptive by artificial bee colony (ABC). This paper discusses Texas instrument fault current detection and MATLAB validation. It improves system reliability, device protection, and copper savings by thousands of tons. ABC intelligently optimizes many mathematical problems. ABC with network neural artificial intelligence (AI) improves algorithm performance (artificial bee colony network neural (ABCNN)). This new method may improve distribution network SLGF detection. This first work can work online in electrical power stations by building the (eZdsp F28335-RS232) into the program to send fault signals to the control when SLGF occurs without damaging devices, equipment, cables, or power outages.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Fault detection is a crucial issue to be considered in the power system to ensure safety, reliability and to avoid accidents, damages to equipment and undesired blackouts. So, processing of the different faults in a distribution network requires different algorithms to detect a fault and extinguish the electric arc. This research work uses in novelty the methods. In the artificial bee colony (ABC) algorithm [1]–[5] has proved its importance in solving a number of the problems including in power system (PS) optimization. ABC algorithm is one of the most methods and novel of based heuristics intelligence. In this paper, the major mission of the

PS protection is to limit the damages to the distribution network in fault or abnormal cases. Besides, a difficulty for relays is to extract information from the voltage and current instruments that indicate that equipment is operating improperly. In this paper focus to the detection single line-to-ground fault (SLGF) and self-extinguishing electric arc using artificial bee colony network neural (ABCNN) control SLGF in distribution network, also working online by used the chip (eZdsp F28335-RS232) in PS by building this in the system. When a fault occurs, this chip sending signal (1) in the fault occur or (0) at no fault, to a control panel. This research focuses for processing of SLG fault in the power distribution system (i.e., 33/11 kV) [6]–[11]. This paper mainly focuses on the protection from the effect of the SLGF in the distribution grid in PS, also preventing equipment and devices from damage. By extinguishing the electric arc in a short period using a PC and the detecting of fault through the ABCNN. Figure 1 a block diagram of the basic configuration of eZdsp F28335 is shown. The main interfaces for eZdsp are the interface and the expansion interface. In these parameters, it converts analog data into digital data.

Figure 1. Block diagram of the basic configuration for the eZdsp F28335

The eZdsp F28335 processing to helps of introduce model-based development and virtual test processes to validate result and test processes optimizing customized development. General improvements it is a query mechanism for searching items in the entire database efficiently and effortlessly. Also, it can explore and help to identify referenced items as well as to use one item in multiple projects and workspaces. This mechanism and automatically connecting service interfaces of the simulation between application and basic software components for the use in practical. This makes the processing easier and faster for achievement [12]–[15].

The eZdsp F28335 is allowing developers to evaluate the TMS320F28335 digital signal controller (DSC) to limited, if it meets their application requirements. Furthermore, the module is an perfect of platform to enhancement and run the software for the TMS320F28335 processor by using the eZdsp F28335 DSC. In Texas instrument at illustrated in Figure 2, mechanical of works between (eZdsp F28335) and MATLAB.

Figure 2. Mechanical of works between eZdsp F28335 and MATLAB

The comprehensive I/O configuration block is used for specifying the hardware setup configuration of DSPACE I/O. This is done by simply connecting the relevant blocks to the Simulink blocks that contain the I/O parameter specification. This can be done anywhere in your model and at a variety of sample rates. Compound I/O boards can have separate blocks for each of their individual purposes [16].

2. METHOD

2.1. DSP2 board with the MATLAB/Simulink

The DSP2 these boards based on the digital signal processor. These blocks enable easy graphical programming of the different control algorithms under the MATLAB/Simulink. The real-time of the practical and the code of the digital signal processors, and it is executed in real-time. The DSP2 library for Simulink in combination with the DSP terminal, which was also developed, and enables easy online monitoring of the DSP2 variables in the text or graphical mode and the parameter tuning, meanwhile the generated code is executed on the DSP2 board. With the DSP2 library for Simulink, the development time of the different control algorithms that are executed on the DSP2 board is reduced. Figure 3, shows a block diagram [17]–[20].

Figure 3. Host side serial monitor (HSSM) used to check the output on the oscilloscopes as well as to transmit the data from the Simulink to the eZdsp F283351

2.2. Experimental results and discussion at (ABCNN Online by using eZdsp F28335)

In this section, we will go through the findings of the experiment. It is the Mechanism eZdsp F28335 for automatically connecting the service interfaces of the simulation between the application and the relevant software components with the intention of making use of them in virtual environments. Because of this, the procedure is made simpler and takes up less time, both of which ultimately contribute to the achievement [21].

2.2.1. ABC method

Artificial bee colony is an artificial technical used for optimization and validation to enhance the system performance. The artificial bee colony optimization algorithm is one of the nature-inspired algorithms. Derived from the behavior of bees and Simulates foods that search for bee habits. This method to be a major contribution to the processing of this problem is that the optimize values based on hybrid ABCNN algorithm. We have dealt with the finding of the optimal methods of Peterson coil values, which specify the value of earth fault current as low as possible. Moreover, we have used two methods to control Peterson coils, such as using the artificial neural fuzzy inference system, and compare to used artificial bee colony to determine the earth's fault current and identify faulty feeder in the distribution network. The contribution of novelty (ABC). That algorithm as to detection single line to ground fault and self- extinguishing at a short time. This method is considered more novelty and no researchers have this used have a good property such as, easy to use interfacing, best solution, fast response as compare with anther algorithm, no needs modeling working with nonlinear system, simple of alteration time, and high quality [22].

Figure 4, represent Simulation at SLGF at the method which is using ABCNN. Also, this method is a hybrid between interface and design then that to be contribution between artificial bee colony and design block in Simulation with neural network.

2.3. ADC interrupt block (IRQ1 (C280× IC28 × 3 ×))

This block called ADC, which is executing a download system. The system algorithm is used to convert analog to digital converter and inside block. Build an ABCNN, also inside it. Three blocks make and give the system to convert the data from Dspace. The system calculator block and the system calculator is used to execute feedback between the desired and actual system finally. This block (feedback) is essential in this Simulink for more robustness and more aquart and with fast response. Al so besides, the data type conversion is also used to calculate the actual values. Monitoring signals using CAN or serial connections: This block is also called serial connection interface (SCI) transmits the data from the Simulink to the SCI. It received by using RS232 cable recommended Serial connection. Also, the system control is used to compare on a line between the desired actual and value. eZdsp F28335: We can use this chap for detection fault online by building this chap in the system to detect fault and process using in the power station at future work. Main contribution Artificial bee colony with fault detection based on artificial intelligence. Stages of processing problem [23].

Figure 4. Simulation at SLGF at adaptive by ABCNN

2.4. eZdsp F28335 description

In the configuration, these block for determine, when the setup configuration of eZdsp F28335 I/O by merely connecting the relevant blocks to the Simulink blocks. Configuration inclusive the block for specifying the hardware setup.in Configuration the eZdsp F28335 will be I/O simply by connecting the relevant blocks to the Simulink blocks in Texas instrument in MATLAB also the parameter specification of the eZdsp F28335 such as voltage level, resolutions, digital I/O, serial interface parameters and validation. Also, can either replace an entire controller with a eZdsp F28335 prototyping system or test new functions by bypassing an existing production controller and all this without manual programming. then the Simulink block diagram design is automatically executing on the system and calculated in real-time therefor eZdsp F28335 offers a wide range of hardware and software components [24], [25]. Figure 5 shows the stages of operation in the laboratory by using MATLAB and eZdsp F28335.

Figure 5. Stages of operation in the laboratory by using MATLAB and eZdsp F28335

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section handles, the experimental result is proposed to execute the system performance artificial bee colony with a neural network. Experimental Simulink need to working, working in discrete and no work continuous and must be cover the data analog to digital. In comparison to the classical methods, found in Figures 6 and 7, in the case of ABCNN, we found the fault current approached the rated current. Also, there is no overshoot, no disturbance, no undershoot, and high system study state. Besides, the duration of the fault is minimal. In comparison to the classical methods found, the results in the case of ABCNN, we found the fault current approached the rated current. Lastly, there was no overshoot, no disturbance, no undershoot, and a high study state. Figure 7 represent best fault and also the duration of the fault is very small as shown in this Figure.

Figure 6. The classical method versus ABCNN

Figure 7. Best result

3.1. Experimental results

This method depended on training+testing+validation, and no used previously in this field. The characterized of these method hybrid ABC+NN can be used online using Texas instrument in MATLAB by building this chip (eZdsp F28335) in power station operation in practical experiences. In review the results of these methods and the comparison between classic methods and novelty method in experimental Simulink need

to working: i) working in discrete and no work continuous and ii) must be cover the data analog to digital. Figure 8 represent compare between the faults current, which are adaptive by classical method PC and ABCNN, in online operation using chip (eZdsp F28335) method in an experimental result (workspace), we can see that have similar values.

Figure 8. Classical and ABCNN experimental result

3.2. Comparison the results between the simulations and (eZdsp F28335-RS232) in taxes instrument MATLAB

In the following Figure 9, we see the difference between the value of the fault current when using classical methods and the value of the fault current when using novel methods ABCNN, which have become compatible with future developments and to become more effective and applied in power station we used eZdsp F28335- RS 232, and when you use it the results were idealistic as we obtained matching results for simulation results and this indicates the possibility of using this method in training in distribution power stations. This work contributes to the detection of SLGF in the shortest period ranging (0.025 sec) in addition to interfacing between mf (simulation) and design (Simulink) by neural network. This work first used ABCNN, and no one has used these methods previously. Figure 9 represent compare between the faults current, which are adaptive by classical method point coil (PC) and ABCNN, in online operation using chip (eZdsp F28335) method in an experimental result (workspace), we can see that have similar values.

Figure 9. ABCNN and classical methods current

4. CONCLUSION

In this project, the significant contribution converts the Simulink working online because most simulations work only theoretically and also validation by using Texas instrument (eZdsp F28335). This method can use in power stations to detect a fault and to process it by building in the system. This chip sending a signal to the control panel when the fault to be an occurrence in (1) which fault and (0) no-fault. Get a good result for fault current became matching rated current for undesired blackout, saving many thousand tons of copper of cable which is bearing when SLGF occurrence in a distribution network and stability voltage in fault and an fault also more accurate, quality and more stable. Fault current was equal to the rated current and at a very ideal time with a value of (0.025 sec). We compare the results of classical methods and modern methods/ and also have no overshoot, no undershoot, and no wave distortions, which produces a steady-state in the power system and high efficiency. The ground this ABC validity in practical use in power plants by connecting and also validation to using taxes instrument (eZdsp F28335).

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